

OXIDATION OF Mn^{II} BY PERSULPHATE IN SULPHURIC ACID MEDIUM

BY YUGUL KISHORE GUPTA AND SATYESHWAR GHOSH

Oxidation reaction of Mn^{II} , catalysed by Ag^+ , has been studied, the kinetics being followed by means of a Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter. The reaction is unimolecular with respect to the persulphate ion and zero-molecular with respect to the manganous ion; the reaction rate is directly proportional to the silver ion concentration. The velocity constants are of the same order as found for other persulphate oxidation reactions, catalysed by the univalent silver ion. All these facts point to the similar mechanism of the reaction. The reaction is likely to be complicated under different conditions due to the occurrence of simultaneous reactions, viz., decomposition of the persulphate catalysed by the silver ion, formation of hydrogen peroxide from persulphate and sulphuric acid, and the interaction of $Mn_2(SO_4)_3$ and H_2O_2 .

The immediate oxidation product of Mn^{II} is trivalent manganese, which is unstable, and its solutions can be stabilised only in the presence of excess of acids. In strong sulphuric acid medium, the salt formed is red-coloured manganic sulphate, $Mn_2(SO_4)_3$. Taube (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 1418) obtained it from the interaction of Mn^{II} and MnO_2 , and used it as a catalyst in the reaction between chlorine and oxalic acid. Davidson (*ibid.*, 1950, 72, 4744) prepared the chloride complex of Mn^{III} by the permanganate oxidation in presence of hydrochloric acid. Oxalate complexes of Mn^{III} , in the reaction between permanganate and oxalate in the presence of manganous ion, have been reported by Gupta and Ghosh (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, under publication). Cartledge and Ericks (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 2061) prepared dioxalate and trioxalate complexes under specified conditions and studied their properties. Citrate complex of Mn^{III} has been reported by Cabrera and Del Rio (*Anal. real Soc., Espan., Fis. y Quim.*, 1953, 49B, 263) and tartrate complex by Pérez and Garcia (*ibid.*, 1953, 49B, 187). Recently Chakravarti and Ghosh (*Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1957, 26A, 41) have obtained $Mn_2(SO_4)_3$ in 7.5M- H_2SO_4 by the dichromate oxidation of Mn^{II} .

Formation of stable $Mn_2(SO_4)_3$ in 3.6M- H_2SO_4 by the persulphate has already been reported by the authors (*Naturwiss.*, 1958, 45, 184). The oxidation is slow as such and, hence, it has been carried out in the presence of silver ions. The kinetics were studied at 22° by means of a Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter. It was first necessary to confirm that the red-coloured compound formed by the persulphate oxidation of Mn^{II} was identical with $Mn_2(SO_4)_3$, obtained by dichromate (D. N. Chakravarti, Doctoral Thesis, 1957, Chapter 2, p. 82) or permanganate (Vogel, "A Text-book of Quantitative and Inorganic Analysis", 1953, p. 312) oxidation. An examination of these by the Unicam spectrophotometer gave the maximum absorption at 505 m μ for all the three differently prepared samples of $Mn_2(SO_4)_3$. Hence, filter No. 50 was used for colorimetric determination of the red-coloured compound. Beer's law was also found to be obeyed within the concentration range investigated.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

All the vessels used in the reaction were of Jena glass and the reaction vessel was coated outside by black Japan to eliminate any photochemical effect. The medium of reaction was water, redistilled from a quartz vessel.

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H.-A.R. quality. Sulphuric acid (d 1.84) was of A.R. quality from Basic and Scientific Chemicals Private Ltd., Calcutta.

Stock solutions of manganous sulphate and silver nitrate were prepared in the usual way and standardised by usual methods. Persulphate solutions were always freshly prepared by direct weighing and the strength checked by the arsenite (Gupta and Ghosh, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1957, 17, 379) and Eckardt's (*Chem. News*, 1900, 81, 38) method.

Known amounts of manganous sulphate, silver nitrate and concentrated sulphuric acid were taken in a reaction vessel and placed in a thermos at 22° . Persulphate solution was kept separately. After these had attained the temperature of the bath, calculated quantity of the persulphate solution was run in the reaction vessel and shaken. At suitable intervals of time, portions of the reaction mixture were taken out and the colorimetric determinations were made. The colorimeter had been standardised previously against the sulphuric acid of the concentrations used in the reaction mixture. Persulphate and the manganous sulphate of the concentrations used had no absorption for filter No. 50.

To compensate the contraction in the volume of the reaction mixture due to addition of sulphuric acid, a calculated quantity of redistilled water was added to the reaction vessel prior to the addition of the persulphate. The temperature of the reaction mixture rose by 1° on the addition of the persulphate solution, but it fell almost to that of the bath within 10 minutes. This slight increase in the temperature in the initial stage could be neglected.

The reaction could not be studied to completion as Beer's law held good only approximately for higher concentrations of $Mn_2(SO_4)_3$, and also due to the limiting concentration of $Mn_2(SO_4)_3$ in solution at a particular H^+ -ion concentration, given by the equilibrium,

Hence with higher concentrations of $Mn_2(SO_4)_3$, formation of MnO_2 occurs, which vitiates the colorimetric readings, and too low a concentration of the persulphate tends to make the reaction very slow for study.

Table I records the calibration of the colorimeter for $Mn_2(SO_4)_3$ prepared from $MnSO_4$ and the permanganate in sulphuric acid of the concentration range 1.8M - 4.95M. This also proves the validity of Beer's law.

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TABLE I

Col. reading.	Conc. of $\text{Mn}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ from iodometry.	Factor for calc. of the conc. of $\text{Mn}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ in <i>N</i> from readings.
63.5	$1.17 \times 10^3 N$	$\frac{4.68 \times 10^{-3}}{254} = 1.85 \times 10^{-5}$.
127	2.34	
254	4.68	
510	9.36	

The reaction rate increases with the increase in the concentration of the persulphate and the reaction is unimolecular with respect to this ion because time of decomposition of any fraction of the persulphate is independent of its original concentration. The reaction is zero-molecular with respect to the manganous ion.) Table II records the results of one experiment at 22°. (The unimolecular constants were calculated from the relation

$$K = \frac{2.303}{t} \times \frac{1}{C_{Ag}} \log \frac{a}{a-x} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where *a* is the initial concentration, *a* - *x*, the concentration after time *t* (in minutes) of the persulphate and *C_{Ag}* is the concentration of the silver nitrate. Persulphate concentration was calculated from $\text{Mn}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ estimated.

TABLE II

$\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8 = 0.02M$. $\text{MnSO}_4 = 0.04M$. $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 3.60M$. $\text{AgNO}_3 = 0.016M$. Temp. = 22°.

Time.	Ccl. reading.	$\text{Mn}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$.	$\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$.	<i>K_{uni}</i> (min. ⁻¹).	Time.	Col. reading.	$\text{Mn}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$.	$\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$.	<i>K_{uni}</i> (min. ⁻¹).
0 min.	0	0	0.0200 M	...	45 min.	244	4.489×10^3	0.01775 M	0.1653
5	33	$0.6071 \times 10^3 N$	0.01969	0.1928	50	270	4.968	0.01751	0.1658
10	64	1.178	0.01941	0.1870	55	292	5.372	0.01731	0.1640
15	93	1.711	0.01914	0.1822	60	315	5.795	0.01710	0.1631
20	117	2.153	0.01892	0.1727	65	340	6.256	0.01687	0.1637
25	149	2.742	0.01862	0.1773	70	363	6.679	0.01666	0.1630
30	170	3.127	0.01843	0.1688	80	400	7.360	0.01632	0.1587
35	200	3.680	0.01816	0.1722	90	452	8.316	0.01584	0.1618
40	224	4.121	0.01793	0.1694	100	500	9.752	0.01512	0.1748
Average									0.1708

From Table II unimolecular constants appear gradually to decrease with the time and this may be ascribed to the decomposition of the persulphate, catalysed by the silver ions, and in accord with our observation that there is a slow and slight evolution of some gas in the reaction mixture. The gas could not be other than oxygen. Tables III and IV record some of the average values of the unimolecular constants with different concentrations of persulphate and of the manganous sulphate.

TABLE III

$\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8 = 0.02M$.		$\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 3.60M$.		$\text{AgNO}_3 = 0.008M$.	
Conc. of $\text{MnSO}_4(M)$	...	0.02	0.04	0.08	0.08
Unimol. const.	...	0.1689	0.1701	0.1717	0.1717

TABLE IV

	$MnSO_4 = 0.04M.$	$H_2SO_4 = 3.60M.$	$AgNO_3 = 0.008M.$
Conc. of $K_2S_2O_8(M)$	0.01	0.02	0.04
Unimol. const.	0.1739	0.1701	0.1756

The effect of varying the concentration of silver nitrate on the reaction rate constants is linear, as is evident from Table V.

TABLE V

	$K_2S_2O_8 = 0.02M.$	$MnSO_4 = 0.04M.$	$H_2SO_4 = 3.60M.$
$AgNO_3 (M)$	... 0.004	0.008	0.016
Unimol. const.	... 0.1677	0.1701	0.1705

In Table VI are shown the colorimetric readings using different concentrations of sulphuric acid.

TABLE VI

Time	H_2SO_4 concentration in molarity.								No. Color.
	$K_2S_2O_8 = 0.02M.$		$MnSO_4 = 0.02M.$					$AgNO_3 = 0.008M.$	
	1.80.	2.70.	3.15.	3.60	4.05.	4.50.	4.95.	5.40	
5 min.	12.5	14.5	14.5	17.6	16.5	18.5	20.0		
10	28.0	28.5	29.5	32.5	32.0	34.5	35.0		
15	40.5	43.5	43.5	46.0	47.0	49.0	48.5		
20	54.0	55.5	57.0	61.0	60.5	63.5	60.5		
25	68.0	68.5	70.5	73.5	74.5	75.5	71.5		
30	82.0	...	83.5	86.5	86.5	87.5	79.5		
35	94.5	95.0	97.0	100.0	99.0	98.5	87.5		
40	107.0	108.5	109.5	113.5	111.0	107.5	92.5		
45	120.0	121.0	121.5	125.0	122.5	116.5	96.5		
50	133.5	135.0	135.5	138.0	132.5	125.5	99.0		
55	147.0	147.0	148.0	150.0	142.5	133.5	101.5		
60	160.0	157.5	159.5	160.0	152.0	138.0	103 *		
70	184.5	183.5	184.0	181.0	169.5	148.5	105.0		
80	208.0	207.5	...	...	166.5	158.5	...		
90	232.0	230.5	...	222.0	204.5	168.0	108.5		
100	255.0	253.5	...	...	...	...	111		
K uni.	0.1589	0.1601	0.1629	0.1689	0.1636	0.1593	0.1582		

* The average of the constants was taken only up to this reading.

It would appear that in the beginning, the colorimetric readings go on increasing with the concentration of the sulphuric acid, but reverse is true at the later stage of the reaction. Also considering all the concentrations of the sulphuric acid, the readings are maximum when the concentration of the sulphuric acid is 3.60 M, at the intervals of 35, 40, 45, 50 and 55 minutes. The slow increase in the colorimetric readings (in the later stage) above 3.6 M concentration of H_2SO_4 , is probably due to the reaction of $Mn_2(SO_4)_3$ with H_2O_2 produced from the persulphate. It should be stated that the mixtures of the persulphate and sulphuric acid respond to the test for H_2O_2 above 3.6 M overall concentration of the sulphuric acid, below which negligible amounts of H_2O_2 are produced. The formation of H_2O_2 in 5.4M- H_2SO_4 is so sufficient as to consume all $Mn_2(SO_4)_3$ from the very start of the reaction. The sharp increase in the readings (in the later stage) below 3.6 M of H_2SO_4 may be due to the tendency of the reaction mixture forming

colloidal MnO_2 for want of sufficient acid to hold Mn^{III} in solution. It is evident from the average values of the unimolecular constants in Table VI and what has been said above, that the most suitable concentration of H_2SO_4 for the formation of $Mn_2(SO_4)_3$ is 3.6 M.

The reaction was also studied at 27° and 32°. Table VII records the average values of the unimolecular constants at these temperatures.

TABLE VII

$K_2S_2O_8 = 0.02M$. $MnSO_4 = 0.02M$. $H_2SO_4 = 3.60M$. $AgNO_3 = 0.008M$.

Temp.	...	22°	27°	32°
Unimol. const.	...	.1689	0.2319	0.3250

The heat of activation calculated by the Arrhenius equation gives the average value of 11670 calories for the range 22-32°. The graphical value was found to be 11740 calories which is in good agreement with the calculated value.

Calculation of the Frequency Factor A

A is given by the relation

$$\log A = \log K + E/2.303RT \quad \dots (2)$$

where all the symbols have the usual significance. Using the average value of the energy of activation, the values of A have been calculated at different temperatures.

TABLE VIII

Temp.	...	22°	27°	32°	
$A \times 10^{-7} \text{ min}^{-1}$	...	8.009	7.875	7.993	Av. 7.959

Calculation of the Entropy of Activation

For a unimolecular reaction, the thermodynamic treatment gives

$$K = (kT/h) e^{\Delta S^\ddagger/R} e^{-E/RT} \quad \dots (3)$$

where 'k' is Boltzmann's constant and 'h' is Planck's constant.

From equations (2) and (3)

$$A = (kT/h) e^{\Delta S^\ddagger/R} \quad \dots (4)$$

and

$$kT/h \approx 10^{13} \quad \dots (5)$$

The energy of activation calculated from equation (4) is -31.37 E.U. All these calculations may be said to be true within the range of the reaction which has been studied here.

Mechanism

The unimolecularity of the reaction with respect to the persulphate ion, zero-molecularity with respect to the manganous ion and direct proportionality to silver-ion concentration, all point to a similar mechanism as advanced by the authors in an earlier paper (Gupta and Ghosh, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, under publication). The value of the unimolecular constant is of the same order as for other reductants such as NH_3 , NH_4^+ , Cr^{3+} or VO^{2+} . The negative entropy of activation

suggests (Frost and Pearson, "Kinetics and Mechanism", John Wiley & Sons Inc., New York, 1953, Chapter 5, pp. 98-99) the reaction taking place between a charged ion and a neutral molecule or between similarly charged ions.

Actually the rate-determining step is between oppositely charged ions as is evident from the following mechanism :

The rate-determining step is (ii).

$$\text{From (ii)} \quad -\frac{dc}{dt} = k_2 [\text{Ag}^+][\text{SO}_4^-]^2$$

$$\text{Also from (i)} \quad K = [\text{SO}_4^-]^2 / [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]$$

where K is the equilibrium constant.

$$\text{Hence} \quad -\frac{dc}{dt} = K k_2 [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}][\text{Ag}^+] = k [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}];$$

where $k = K k_2 [\text{Ag}^+]$.

The experimentally measured constant is equal to $k/[\text{Ag}^+]$.

$$\therefore k_2 = \frac{k}{[\text{Ag}^+]K} = \frac{1.689}{K}$$

[Now K will be small of the order of 10^{-8}]

$$\therefore k_2 = \frac{1.689}{10^{-8}} = 1.689 \times 10^7 \text{ litres moles}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}.$$

Calculation of the frequency factor and the entropy of activation of the rate-determining step (ii) gives the values 13.35×10^{13} and 5.13 E.U. This indicates the reaction between oppositely charged ions. It must be seen here that the values do not support the generally accepted mechanism,

because observed values of frequency factor and the entropy are low. This makes clear that the slow reaction step is not between $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ and Ag^+ , but between Ag^+ and some product of S_2O_8 which is negatively charged.